

Modern Solutions for Complications after Rhinoplasty Today

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Abstract: Has extensive experience in performing septoplasty operations. The modern techniques available to our doctors allow us not only to operate using the latest advances in medicine, but also to ensure the comfort of the client in the postoperative period: it significantly reduces pain and allows breathing immediately after the operation.

Key words: Frequently asked questions about septoplasty, Why nasal packing is necessary after the operation, At the end of the operation, the doctor places tampons in the nasal cavity to prevent bleeding. Therefore, you should breathe through your mouth during the first day after the operation.

Why does my nose bleed after surgery?

Postoperative bleeding is normal in the first 12 hours after surgery.

➤ Why does dry mouth appear after surgery?

After surgery, you may experience dry mouth. It depends on the drugs used during anesthesia.

➤ Why can't you blow your nose or sneeze during rehabilitation?

This can damage the healing tissue that was operated on and cause complications. If you want to sneeze, you should sneeze with your mouth open, this will reduce the tension in the nasal cavity.

➤ Why do bruises appear on cheeks and eyelids after surgery?

In rare cases, but still there are postoperative events such as slight swelling or traces of bruises in the area of the cheeks and eyelids. This often happens if, in addition to the nasal septum, surgery has been performed on the paranasal sinuses. Usually, the swelling increases on the second day and starts to decrease in the next 5-6 days. Postoperative swelling and bruising do not indicate the quality of the operation and do not affect the postoperative result.

➤ How long are the tires installed?

After removing tampons from the nasal cavity, silicone tires remain in the nose. They are usually placed for a period of 3 days to 2 weeks depending on the goals set by the surgeon. If the tires are dirty, carefully read the doctor's instructions on how to clean them.

➤ How often should you visit the doctor after the operation?

On average, 3-4 visits are required during the rehabilitation period. In the postoperative period, it is important to come to the doctor to check the nasal cavity and go to the toilet. This helps to speed up the recovery of the respiratory function of the nose.

➤ Why does blood-like pink fluid flow from the throat and nose after septoplasty?

A few days after the operation, a pinkish-red liquid may flow from the nose and throat - this is discharge. Over time, the amount of such discharge decreases until it stops completely. But this flow

should not be confused with bleeding that often occurs after surgery. If you have a nosebleed for a long time, you should immediately consult a doctor.

- What should I do if my nose hurts a lot after packing?

After surgery, patients complain of discomfort caused by tampons in the nose. If there is pain, you should take painkillers as prescribed by the doctor.

- What should be done if the crusts formed in the nose cause pain or interfere?

You can gently clean the crusts around the nostrils without going inside. This is done with cotton balls soaked in a 3% solution of hydrogen peroxide.

- After the operation, my ear and head hurt a lot, what caused it?

Discomfort in the ears and head is normal in the postoperative period. In this case, you should ask your doctor to prescribe a pain reliever.

- What is the risk of infection in the nasal cavity after septoplasty?

The risk of postoperative wound infection after septoplasty is very low. However, if there is pain, swelling, redness and body temperature in the nasal area rises to 38 degrees, this may be a sign of infection. You should report this to your doctor and come for an examination.

- Why does my throat hurt after septoplasty?

One of the most common complaints after surgery is a sore throat. This is because a special tube is inserted into the throat during anesthesia. After its removal, discomfort in the throat may remain. Sensations usually disappear within a few days.

- Lips and teeth become dull after septoplasty. What is it about?

A feeling of numbness in the area of the teeth and upper lips often worries the patient. This is due to the swelling of the nerve nodes. This is not something to be afraid of. Sensitivity usually returns within a few weeks.

- What should be avoided during rehabilitation?

For 2-3 weeks after surgery, you should limit physical activity, do not bend your head down, do not lift or push heavy objects. Avoid hot water procedures (baths, saunas, etc.).

- Is it possible to smoke during rehabilitation?

Smoking in the postoperative period, as well as in rooms with tobacco smoke, is contraindicated, because it causes swelling and impairs the healing of the operated tissues.

- How much does it cost to give up alcohol after surgery?

In the first 10 days after the operation, it is strictly forbidden to drink alcohol - when you drink alcohol, the risk of bleeding from the operated surfaces increases significantly!

List of used literature:

1. Baxriyevich, U. U. B., & Ergashivich, Q. I. (2023). BOLALAR VA O'SMIRLAR SALOMATLIGINING GIGIYENIK BAHOLASH. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(9), 1027-1035.
2. Mahramovna, M. M., Chorshanbievich, K. N., & Ergashovich, K. I. (2023). HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS STUDENTS HEALTHY LIFESTYLE DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(2), 410-413.
3. Ergashovich, K. I., & Bakhriyevich, U. U. (2023). Toxic infections and intoxications caused by food. *IQRO JURNALI*, 2(1), 181-186.

4. Corshanbiyevich, X. N., Narmuratovich, R. Z., Ergashovich, K. I., & TOGRI OVATLANISH, M. E. Y. O. R. L. A. R. I. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal.–2022. T, 10(11), 160-163.
5. Sh, B. R., Ch, X. N., & Kiyamov, I. E. (2022). Environmentally Friendly Product is a Pledge of Our Health. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 9, 48-50.
6. Corshanbiyevich, X. N., Narmuratovich, R. Z., & Ergashovich, K. I. (2022). TOGRI OVATLANISH MEYORLARI. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(11), 160-163.
7. Bakhriyevich, U. U. B., & Abdurakhmonovna, E. M. (2023). ROLE OF THE OZONE LAYER IN BIOLOGICAL PROCESSES. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 1(9), 1019-1026.
8. Kiyomov, I., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). IMPROVING SURGICAL TREATMENT METHODS FOR PATIENTS WITH NASAL PATHOLOGY. Science and innovation, 2(D11), 226-231.
9. Qiyomov Ixtiyor Ergashevich. (2024). Modern Methods of Treating Nosebleeds. Journal of Science in Medicine and Life, 2(5), 554–559.
10. Qiyomov Ixtiyor Ergashevich. (2024). Modern Methods of Treating Nosebleeds. Journal of Science in Medicine and Life, 2(5), 548–553.
11. Qiyomov Ixtiyor Ergashevich. (2024). Improvement of Surgical Treatment Methods in Patients With Nasal Pathologies. Journal of Science in Medicine and Life, 2(5), 540–547.
12. Farrukh S. ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 8. – С. 493-499.
13. Rustamovich, A. I., Negmatovich, T. K., & Fazliddinovich, S. D. (2022). БОЛАЛИКДАН БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДА РИНОСИНСИТИ БОР БЕМОРЛАРДА БУРУН БЎШЛИҒИ МУКОЦИЛИАР ТРАНСПОРТИ НАЗОРАТИ ТЎҒРИСИДАГИ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР (адабиётлар шарҳи). JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 7(2).
14. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2021). Эффективность применения местной антибиотикотерапии в лечении параназального синусита у детей с церебральным параличом. In НАУКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ: СОХРАНЯЯ ПРОШЛОЕ, СОЗДАЁМ БУДУЩЕЕ (pp. 336-338).
15. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2021). Болаликдан бош мия фалажи билан болалардаги ўткир ва сурункали параназал синуситларни даволашда мукорегуляр дори воситасини самарадорлигини ўрганиш. Т [a_XW [i [S US S_S^[Ûe YfcS^, 58.
16. Siddikov, O., Daminova, L., Abdurakhmonov, I., Nuralieva, R., & Khaydarov, M. OPTIMIZATION OF THE USE OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS DURING THE EXACERBATION OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, 32, 2.
17. Тураев, Х. Н. (2021). Абдурахмонов Илхом Рустамович Влияние будесонида на качество жизни пациентов с бронхиальным обструктивным синдромом. Вопросы науки и образования, 7, 132.
18. Абдурахманов, И., Шамсиев, Д., & Олимжонова, Ф. (2021). Изучение эффективности мукорегулярных препаратов в лечении острого и хронического параназального синусита при детском церебральном параличе. Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, 2(2), 18-21.

19. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2023). БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДАГИ ПАРАНАЗАЛ СИНУСИТЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШДА ЎЗИГА ХОС ЁНДАШИШ. MedUnion, 2(1), 14-26.
20. Орипов, Р. А., Абдурахмонов, И. Р., Ахмедов, Ш. К., & Тураев, Х. Н. (2021). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АНТИОКСИДАНТНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ НЕЙРОДЕРМИТА.
21. Ахмедов, Ш. К., Тураев, Х. Н., Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Орипов, Р. А. (2021). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТАКТИКИ ПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ КРАПИВНИЦЫ.
22. Абдурахмонов, И. Р. (2021). Исследование мукоцилиарной транспортной функции слизистой оболочки полости носа у больных с параназальным синуситом на фоне детского церебрального паралича. In Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности (pp. 256-259).
23. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Тураев, Х. Н. (2022). ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ СИНУПРЕТА С АНТИБАКТЕРИАЛЬНЫМИ ПРЕПАРАТАМИ В КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ РИНОСИНУСИТОВ У БОЛЬНЫХ ДЕТСКИМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ. Достижения науки и образования, (2 (82)), 88-92.
24. Abdurakhmanov, I., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN. Science and innovation, 2(D10), 164-168.